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* **Corresponding author.**

visitmalathi@gmail.com

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Intelligent Deep Learning-aided Malicious Node Detection and Encrypted Routing Optimization in Software-Defined Networking

V Mangaiyarkarasi¹, S Malathi^{2*}

1 A. Veeriyar Vandayar Memorial Sri Pushpam College (Autonomous, Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli), Poondi-613503, Thanjavur (DT), Tamil Nadu, India
2 Department of Computer Science, Swami Dayananda College of Arts & Science (Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli), Manjakkudi, Tiruvarur (DT), Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract

Objectives: This study aims to develop a secure and efficient routing framework for Software-Defined Networking (SDN) environments that can dynamically adapt to network changes while mitigating malicious activities.

Method: A deep learning (DL)-assisted secure routing system is proposed, where a network emulator is employed to simulate real-time network operations with virtual hosts, OpenFlow switches, and communication links. A centralized controller manages traffic flow and installs forwarding rules dynamically. Flow-level statistics are collected from both normal and attack traffic. A Gated Convolution Kolmogorov-Arnold Network (GCKAN) is utilized for detecting malicious nodes through traffic pattern classification. For secure communication, a hybrid Elliptic Curve ElGamal Diffie-Hellman (ECE-DH) scheme is applied for key exchange. Furthermore, the Draco Lizard Optimization (DLO) algorithm is adopted to determine optimal and secure routing paths. **Findings:** The proposed framework demonstrates superior performance in terms of security and efficiency. It achieves over 95% accuracy in malicious node detection, reduces energy consumption by 30%, and decreases communication distance by 45%. Comparative analysis with existing methods confirms the effectiveness of the model in enhancing secure routing within SDN-IoT environments. **Novelty:** The study integrates GCKAN-based malicious node detection, ECE-DH secure key exchange, and DLO-based optimal routing within a unified SDN framework. This combined approach ensures enhanced security, efficient routing, and adaptability to dynamic network conditions.

Keywords: Software-Defined Networking (SDN); Malicious Node Detection; Data Encryption; Secure Optimal Routing Framework; Deep Learning (DL); Draco Lizard Optimization (DLO)

1 Introduction

The rapid growth of networked devices and network traffic has created a complex communication network, and there is a need for intelligent and adaptive management⁽¹⁾. This is where SDN plays a vital role by using a decoupled control and data plane, centralized control, programmability, and dynamic management⁽²⁾. However, traditional routing protocols used in SDN have limitations, as they use static and limited metrics, and hence cannot efficiently handle dynamic traffic, resulting in network congestion and poor Quality of Service (QoS)⁽³⁾. Existing breakthroughs in Traffic Engineering (TE) in SDN have been based on deep learning and reinforcement learning techniques⁽⁴⁾. These techniques offer promising flexibility; however, they face major drawbacks such as: (i) underutilization of network state information in real-time, (ii) scalability and accuracy issues in large network scenarios, and (iii) lack of consideration of critical factors such as bandwidth, latency, and traffic at the node level⁽⁵⁾. In addition, most of the solutions focus on security and routing as individual entities, where detection of malicious nodes in the network is delayed, and routing decisions are not aware of security attacks. Moreover, encryption techniques are computationally expensive and inflexible in dynamic network scenarios⁽⁶⁾.

Li *et al.* (2024)⁽⁷⁾ presented a model for the control of malware propagation based on abnormal traffic detection and an advanced SIR framework. Although the model was analytically sound, there were certain assumptions based on homogeneous interactions and detection rates, which are not feasible in heterogeneous and uncertain network scenarios. Javadpour *et al.* (2025)⁽⁸⁾ presented a game-theoretic botnet detection mechanism based on the concept of the Mafia game. Although the mechanism was effective in modeling adversarial scenarios, there were certain limitations in terms of scalability and the consideration of multiple factors in network scenarios. Hatamleh *et al.* (2025)⁽⁹⁾ have presented a multi-layer SDN-IoT architecture for security, using blockchain and deep reinforcement learning. Though there was improvement in terms of accuracy, there is a significant amount of complexity involved.

Gunavathie and Umamaheswari (2024)⁽¹⁰⁾ have presented a GRU-based traffic-aware routing scheme. The performance of this scheme was largely dependent on the quality of historical data and is not suitable for sudden changes. Chen *et al.* (2024)⁽¹¹⁾ have presented a metaheuristic-based optimizer for routing, using exploration capabilities, which was complex and is largely dependent on parameter settings.

The significant contributions of the introduced framework are as follows:

- To design a DL-assisted secure routing framework capable of identifying and mitigating malicious activities within an SDN environment.
- To utilize the Gated Convolution Kolmogorov–Arnold Network (GCKAN) for accurate classification of normal and attack traffic based on flow-level statistics.
- To establish a secure communication mechanism using a hybrid Elliptic Curve ElGamal Diffie–Hellman (ECE-DH) scheme for protected key exchange among trusted nodes.
- To optimize data delivery paths through the Draco Lizard Optimization (DLO) algorithm, ensuring efficient and secure routing after isolating compromised entities.

The subsequent sections are structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the proposed methodology, Section 3 presents the results and discussion, and Section 4 presents the conclusion.

2 Methodology

A secure routing architecture supported by DL techniques was designed to counter malicious behavior in an SDN environment. Figure 1 depicts the workflow of the developed framework.

2.1 Clustered Architecture using SDN Controllers

The architecture of an IoT-enabled SDN architecture is designed based on a cluster hierarchy, where a cluster behaves as an independent domain controlled by an SDN controller to minimize latency, communication overhead, and efficiently manage resources. The storage of data in a centralized manner, along with a verification mechanism, enables secure communication, tracing, and eliminates the possibility of a single point of failure. To cater to resource-constrained devices, complex operations are performed by the controller, whereas dynamic node mobility between domains enhances energy efficiency.

- ***File Transfer (FT) Process in Clustered SDN***

The file transfer process in the clustered SDN network is based on a controller-assisted FT mechanism, where the IoT devices are authenticated, and data is securely encrypted using the Elliptic Curve ElGamal Diffie–Hellman key exchange algorithm before

Fig 1. Workflow of the developed Framework

communication. During intra- and inter-cluster communication, trust is established by the SDN controllers, and optimized routing is used for efficient data communication. At the receiver side, the encrypted data is decrypted using shared keys, thus facilitating secure, authenticated, and lightweight communication without using the blockchain technology.

2.2 Malicious Node Detection using GCKAN Technique

The GCKAN is trained on these features to learn both topological dependencies and operational dynamics in the network, which helps to identify abnormal activities with high accuracy⁽¹²⁾. The communication model considered several energy-related parameters to evaluate the behavior of IoT devices during data transmission.

- **Initial Energy**(E_i^0)

Each IoT node was assigned a fixed initial energy at network deployment:

$$E_i^0 = E_{init}, \forall i \in N \tag{1}$$

Here, N signifies the set of IoT devices.

- **Transmission Energy**(E_{tx})

The energy consumed for transmitting a packet of size L bits over distance d is modeled as:

$$E_{tx}(L, d) = L \cdot E_{elec} + L \cdot \epsilon_{amp} \cdot d^\alpha \tag{2}$$

Here, E_{elec} denotes the electronic circuitry energy, ϵ_{amp} signifies the amplifier coefficient, and α symbolizes the path-loss exponent.

- **Energy for Packet Acceptance**(E_{acc})

The energy required for processing and accepting an incoming packet is defined as:

$$E_{acc}(L) = L \cdot E_{proc} \tag{3}$$

Here, E_{proc} represents processing energy per bit.

- **Channel Energy Dissipation**(E_{dis})

Energy lost to the environment during transmission is expressed as:

$$E_{dis} = L \cdot \epsilon_{loss} \cdot d^\alpha \tag{4}$$

Here, ϵ_{loss} characterizes channel attenuation losses.

- **Receiving Energy**(E_{rx})

The per-packet reception energy cost at a node is calculated as:

$$E_{rx}(L) = L \cdot E_{elec} \tag{5}$$

- **Current Energy of Node**($E_i(t)$)

The residual energy of the node i at time t is updated dynamically:

$$E_i(t) = E_i(t-1) - (E_{tx} + E_{rx} + E_{acc}) \tag{6}$$

- **Distance Between Two Nodes**(d_{ij})

The Euclidean distance between nodes i and j is determined by:

$$d_{ij} = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \tag{7}$$

- **Distance Threshold**(d_{th})

A constraint is imposed to ensure energy-efficient communication:

$$d_{ij} \leq d_{th} \tag{8}$$

Here, links exceeding d_{th} were avoided or rerouted.

- **Remaining Energy After Transmission**(E_{rem})

The available energy following a communication event is computed as:

$$E_{rem} = E_i^0 - \sum_{k=1}^m E_{consumed}^{(k)} \tag{9}$$

Here, m denotes the number of transmissions handled by the node i . After data generation, malicious nodes are detected in the SDN environment.

In order to detect malicious nodes, a Gated Convolution Kolmogorov-Arnold Network (GCKAN) is used, which analyzes the node features to classify the nodes into malicious or genuine ones. This model is also used to filter out malicious nodes in the selection of the cluster head, ensuring that only genuine nodes are used to handle the coordination and communication in the network. To avoid the high computation complexity of KAN models, GCKAN uses an adaptive nonlinear scaling approach, which is based on the Kolmogorov-Arnold representation. Notably, for a continuous mapping $f : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$, there exist sets of continuous univariate functions $\phi_{x,y} : [0, 1]^n \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ and outer functions $\phi_x : \mathfrak{R} \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ such that the function f can be expressed accordingly.

$$f(p_1, \dots, p_m) = \sum_{x=1}^{2m+1} \phi_x \left(\sum_{y=1}^m \phi_{x,y}(p_y) \right) \tag{10}$$

The univariate functions ϕ are modeled using B-spline representations, where the parameter estimates with the local B-spline basis functions are treated as trainable parameters. For a given input, $H \in \mathfrak{R}^{m_{in}}$, a KAN layer obtains $X \in \mathfrak{R}^{m_{out}}$ through the 1D matrix functions:

$$X_i = \sum_{j=1}^{m_{in}} \phi_{ij}(H_j), i = 1, \dots, m_{out} \tag{11}$$

Here, ϕ_{ij} signifies the edge function, which is defined by a B-spline joined with a residual parameter:

$$\phi_{ij}(v) = w_{ij}^{(b)} b(v) + w_{ij}^{(r)} spline(v) \tag{12}$$

Here, $b(v) = silu(v) = \frac{v}{(1+\exp(-v))}$, $spline(v)$ symbolizes the B-spline linear combination in which $spline(v) = \sum_j k_j B_j(v)$, where k_j signifies the trainable parameter. The **equations (19) and (20)** capture the essence of the core design: a node pools the

received signals, and the links between nodes apply one-dimensional, trainable activation functions approximated with splines. One addition introduces a residual branch to make training more stable and optimization more reliable.

To speed up the training and improve computational efficiency, the FastKAN setting is utilized, where B-spline functions are replaced by Gaussian radial basis functions (RBFs), which are defined as:

$$B_j(v) \approx \exp\left(-\frac{(v - \lambda_g)^2}{2\sigma_g^2}\right) \tag{13}$$

Here, λ_g represents the fixed mid-point, and σ_g are static, distributed bandwidth defined using grid spacing that stabilizes the RBF extensions. This replacement keeps the same structure as described in **Equation (11)** while allowing for more efficient computations, optimized for GPUs, with comparable performance. With regards to our architecture, the formula described in **Equation (13)** is used as an encoding in each node before iterative information exchange in the GNN.

After the stage of node representation encoding, the information is transmitted over a pre-defined graph using a series of GCN layers. Leveraging the first-order approximations for localized graph spectral filters, the update function used for each GCN layer can be expressed as:

$$H^{(u+1)} = \sigma\left(\widetilde{M}^{-1/2} \widetilde{N} \widetilde{M}^{-1/2} H^{(u)} W^{(u)}\right) \tag{14}$$

Here, $\widetilde{N} = N + I_G$ signifies the undirected graph having an adjacency matrix with fused self-links, I_G demonstrates the identity matrix, $\widetilde{M}_{jj} = \sum_i \widetilde{N}_{ji}$, W symbolizes the layer-based trainable matrix, $H^{(u)} \in \mathfrak{R}^{G \times M}$ denotes the activation matrix in u^{th} layer, $H^{(0)} = L$, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ interprets the activation function. The proposed GC-KAN technique uses leakyReLU having 0.01 negative gradient as the activation function. During training, a weighted reconstruction loss is computed on the predicted attack maps L_t and attack extent/thickness maps H_t rather than directly penalizing intermediate residual representations, as expressed in **equation (15)**.

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(x) &= \\ &= x^2 \left[\beta_z \|\widehat{\Delta}z_t - \Delta z_t\|_2^2 + \beta_h \|\widehat{\Delta}H_t - \Delta H_t\|_2^2 \right] \\ &= \\ &= x^2 \left[\beta_z \|z_t - z_t\|_2^2 + \beta_h \|H_t - H_t\|_2^2 \right] \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

To balance learning priorities and heterogeneous noise levels between malicious presence and malicious extent, the aggregate loss is expressed as a weighted sum of two independent MSE terms, controlled by coefficients β_l and β_h , respectively.

2.3 Data Encryption using ECE-DH Technique

After the malicious nodes have been detected, the data to be received is encrypted to enhance the security of the SDN network. To do this, the Elliptic Curve ElGamal Diffie-Hellman (ECEDH) algorithm is proposed⁽¹³⁾. This algorithm enables the computation of a shared secret between the two nodes participating in the data transfer. The computation is done using elliptic curve mathematics. Each node computes a private key and a public point on the elliptic curve, allowing both nodes to compute the same shared secret without actually sending it. The shared secret is then used to encrypt the data to be sent.

Assume two parties intend to establish a shared secret key. Let p be a large prime number, and consider an EC E defined over the Galois field \mathbb{Z}_p by the equation,

$$y^2 \equiv x^2 + ux + v \pmod{p} \tag{16}$$

Here, u and v represents the curve parameters that satisfy the non-singularity condition. Let $M = (a_M, b_M)$ be a base point (generator) on the curve E . The set $E(\mathbb{Z}_p)$ contains all points on the curve, and its total number of elements is denoted by $\#E$ (the order of the curve). The allowable private keys are selected from the integer interval $\{2, 3, \dots, \#E - 1\}$. Thus, the public domain parameters used by both participants are $(p, u, v, M(a_M, b_M))$. For integrated ECEDH, choose a generator $\alpha \in \{2, 3, \dots, p - 2\}$ of the multiplicative group \mathbb{Z}_p , and select a base point $M = (a_M, b_M)$ on the EC that serves as the reference point for scalar multiplication. Accordingly, the public domain parameters shared by communicating entities are (p, u, v, M) .

Using these parameters, both parties compute intermediate values i, j , and the point (r, s) through elliptic-curve operations, which together enable the derivation of a common secret. This shared information is then employed to construct the encryption and decryption key matrices. The encryption key is evaluated as,

$$H = \tilde{\delta}_e^f \pmod{67} \tag{17}$$

While the corresponding inverse key used for decryption is formulated as,

$$H^{-1} = (\tilde{\delta}_e^{-1})^f \pmod{67} \tag{18}$$

This allows both secure key agreement and protected data exchange within a unified framework.

2.4 Secure Routing using DLO Technique

This manuscript proposes an innovative Draco lizard optimizer (DLO)⁽¹⁴⁾ for improved cluster head selection (CHS) in SDN. Additionally, its adaptive coloration and patterned wing membranes allow it to blend with foliage and tree bark, enhancing survival in rainforest environments.

Step 1: Initialization Phase

Within the DLO algorithm, a population consisting of M DLs are considered, with each operating in a D -dimensional search space. The position of each lizard is defined by a position vector P , which represents its current state in the search domain. Accordingly, the position vector P can be mathematically expressed as shown in **equation (19)**.

$$P = [\vec{P}_0, \vec{P}_1, \vec{P}_2, \dots, \vec{P}_{M-1}] \tag{19}$$

Here, \vec{P}_x indicates the location vector of x^{th} DL, which can be formulated as,

$$\vec{P}_x = [P_{x,0}, P_{x,1}, P_{x,2}, \dots, P_{x,D-1}] \tag{20}$$

Step 2: Random Generation

The vectors arbitrarily created in the solution space, subject to the limitations assigned in the case of the given problem, become the input vectors upon initialization. The input vectors, so created, are the possible candidate solutions to be operated on in the process of optimization.

Step 3: Fitness Function

For a candidate node i communicating with the node j , the DLO evaluates each candidate node using a multi-objective fitness function, which can be formulated as,

$$f_i = w_1 \cdot \frac{E_{consumed}^i}{E_{max2} \frac{\sum d_{ij}}{d_{max3}^{penalty} (1 - E_{ratio}^i)}} \tag{21}$$

Here, $E_{consumed}^i$ denotes the energy consumed during transmission, $\sum d_{ij}$ symbolizes the centrally located nodes,

$D_{penalty}^i = \begin{cases} 0, & d_{ij} \leq d_{th} \\ \frac{d_{ij}}{d_{th}}, & d_{ij} > d_{th} \end{cases}$ demonstrates the distance penalty to avoid long links, $1 - E_{ratio}^i$ signifies the prevention of

low-energy nodes from becoming CH, whereas, $E_{ratio}^i = \frac{E_{rem}^i}{E_0^i}$.

Step 4: Flight Manoeuvring and spatial navigation

The corresponding search formulation is presented in **equation (22)**.

$$p_x(k+1) = \begin{cases} p_{best_x} + rand. \left(\vec{p}_n(k) - X \cdot p_{best_x} \right) + \vec{DL} \cdot rand \\ \cdot \left(\vec{p}_n(k) - \vec{p}_m(k) \right), \text{ if } f \left(p_{best_x} \right) > f \left(p_{best_n} \right) \\ p_{best_x} + rand. \left(p_{best_x} - \vec{p}_n(k) \right) + \\ \cdot \vec{DL} \cdot rand. \left(\vec{p}_n(k) - \vec{p}_m(k) \right), \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{22}$$

Here, \vec{pbest}_x represents the candidate's locally achieved best state location vector for x^{th} solution vector, whereas, $rand$ indicates the arbitrary number of D -dimensional search space, each observing the unvarying dispersal between the range 0 and 1, $\vec{p}_n(k)$ and $\vec{p}_m(k)$ demonstrates the location vector of two various DL arbitrarily chosen from the population, k signifies the number of existing iterations, and $k + 1$ denotes the number of present iterations, f denotes the fitness function. The arbitrary number X is obtained by **equation (23)**,

$$X = round(1 + rand(0, 1)) \tag{23}$$

Here, X indicates the value of 1 or 2, and $round$ signifies the rounding function.

Step 5: Concealment mechanisms combined with dynamic movement control

When it is threatened, the Draco lizard is highly adaptable in deciding between hiding or escaping. Similarly, when $k < K_{max}$, the DLO algorithm initiates solution refinement, and the search area gradually shrinks. However, to escape local optima, it incorporates both the Lévy flight surrounding the global optimal solution and Adaptive Gaussian Mutation, simulating rapid escape and camouflage actions. A probability parameter i controls switching between these strategies, allowing the algorithm to adjust dynamically in later iterations.

$$p_x(k+1) = \begin{cases} \vec{gbest} + levy(D) \cdot (\vec{gbest} - \vec{p}_v(k)), & \text{if } rand(0, 1) < i \\ \vec{gbest} + o \cdot \left(1 - k/K_{max}\right) (\vec{pbest}_x - \vec{p}_v(k)) \end{cases} \tag{24}$$

Here, $i = 0.2$, k signifies the present iterations, K_{max} denotes the maximum iteration, \vec{gbest} denotes the optimal location vector in the DL population. o signifies the arbitrary number distributed normally with a variance of 10 and a mathematical expectation of 0.

Step 6: Locally optimal selection method

Upon completion of each repetition, the DLO uses an acquisitive update procedure to apprise both the best personal positions of the search entity and the best overall solution found by the population. The mathematical equations that formulate these update procedures are given by **equations (25) and (26)**.

$$\vec{pbest}_x = \begin{cases} p_x(k+1), & \text{if } f(p_x(k+1)) < f(\vec{pbest}_x) \\ \vec{pbest}_x, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{25}$$

$$\vec{gbest} = \begin{cases} p_x(k+1), & \text{if } f(p_x(k+1)) < f(\vec{gbest}) \\ \vec{gbest}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{26}$$

Here, $p_x(k+1)$ denotes x^{th} DL vector obtained during the present iteration, and $k + 1$ indicates the present iteration.

Step 7: Return the Best Optimal Solution

Step 8: Termination criteria

The introduced DLO method moves to the next phase on the basis of the DLO, whereby the process of updating is reiterated through equations until the desired stopping conditions are fulfilled. After the whole process is complete, the globally optimal solution that has been developed from the reiterated processes is selected and used as the final solution for CH selection in the SDN network.

3 Results and Discussion

The introduced methodology is developed using the Python environment and tested in a controlled experimental setting. The critical hyperparameters are defined as follows: the learning rate is set to 0.001 to regulate the gradient descent step size, the batch size is kept constant at 64 for mini-batch learning, the dropout coefficient is set to 0.2 to mitigate the overfitting phenomenon, and the model is trained for 300 epochs to obtain stable convergence dynamics. All numerical computations are performed on a computing platform with an Intel Core i5-4300M processor, 4 GB memory, and a 64-bit OS structure. During the optimization process, the total number of search iterations is considered to be 2000, and the metaheuristic optimization algorithm is iterated over 10 independent runs to obtain stable results.

3.1 Dataset Description

The input data for the Manuscript is obtained from the CICIoT2023 Dataset⁽¹⁵⁾, which is a large network traffic dataset. It has over 46 million network flow records with 46-47 traffic features, such as flow duration, packet length statistics, protocol type, packet rate, header length, and byte counts. The data records are either benign or malicious, with 33 distinct forms of attacks belonging to major categories such as Denial of Service (DoS), Distributed DoS (DDoS), brute force, reconnaissance, spoofing, and Mirai botnet attacks.

3.2 Evaluation of the Proposed Strategy in Comparison with Conventional Methods

This section presents a visual assessment highlighting the performance improvements of the introduced method relative to conventional approaches. A set of established techniques is used as benchmarks to evaluate the introduced framework. A detailed discussion of the observed performance outcomes is provided in the following subsections:

Fig 2. Convergence Analysis focusing on diverse optimizers, (a) Optimal CHS, and (b) Optimal Routing

Figure 2(a-b) indicates the convergence Analysis focusing on diverse optimizers across optimal CHS and routing, respectively. The introduced ECEDH-GCKAN-DLO model converges very quickly and steadily because the DLO process is able to control the strategic balance between global search and Local Refinement of the search space during the selection of the cluster-head. In Figure 2(b), the proposed approach ECEDH-GCKAN-DLO helps the objective function to converge to stability quickly since the encrypted trust validation and topology-aware learning facilitate the optimization process to focus on the feasible regions. The traditional methods have abrupt changes and stagnation, showing inefficient parameter updates.

Table 1. Experimental breakdown of communication distance across varying numbers of rounds

Rounds	PSO	GWO	CSA	SMO	N-SMO	Proposed (ECEDH-GCKAN-DLO)
400	1350	1250	1180	1100	950	725
800	1550	1450	1420	1380	1000	790
1200	1480	1400	1360	1300	900	750
1600	1420	1320	1280	1200	750	735
2000	1500	1430	1380	1320	1120	760

Table 1 depicts the experimental breakdown of communication distance across varying numbers of rounds. The proposed ECEDH-GCKAN-DLO framework always provides shorter communication distances because routing paths are filtered through secure node verification before optimization. The existing approaches only optimize the distance without tightly coupling security, which may introduce malicious or inefficient relay nodes into the path. This approach introduces indirect routing and more transmission hops. The proposed ECEDH-based authentication ensures that only trusted nodes are involved in the route formation. In contrast, existing approaches consider security as an external component, which may cause a mismatch between trust assessment and path formation.

Fig 3. Energy Consumption (EC) Analysis across varying numbers of rounds

Figure 3 denotes energy consumption analysis across a varying number of rounds. The energy consumption is more balanced in the proposed approach because of its energy-aware fitness function formulation and intelligent node filtering. The GCKAN model predicts behavioral reliability, which prevents the unnecessary involvement of unreliable devices. Conventional methods rely mostly on residual energy heuristics, which are incapable of capturing dynamic interaction patterns. Consequently, energy dissipation builds up unevenly in clusters. The proposed optimizer balances communication tasks more evenly. This avoids early node death. Hence, the network experiences lower cumulative power consumption.

Table 2. Experimental breakdown of security analysis across varying numbers of rounds

Rounds	PSO	GWO	CSA	SMO	N-SMO	Proposed (ECEDH-GCKAN-DLO)
400	450	800	1300	1500	1500	1600
800	100	750	1150	1180	1200	1250
1200	50	820	900	950	1750	1800
1600	450	500	600	650	1420	1500
2000	120	350	520	680	1600	1700

Table 2 depicts the experimental breakdown of security analysis across varying numbers of rounds. The proposed ECEDH-GCKAN-DLO outperforms in terms of security since elliptic-curve cryptography is directly integrated into the routing optimization process, providing confidentiality and trust simultaneously. Conventional models usually deploy encryption or anomaly detection separately, still having vulnerabilities during route setup. Without cryptographic validation, malicious nodes can still affect topology selection. The ECEDH module protects control messages, and GCKAN concurrently detects behavioral anomalies. Conventional models do not provide this dual-layer protection. Their detection rates are also affected during coordinated attacks. The proposed ECEDH-GCKAN-DLO system provides continuous protection throughout communication processes. This holistic approach provides a more robust SDN-IoT environment.

Figure 4 denotes trust analysis across a varying number of rounds. Trust evaluation in the proposed system is fueled by graph-based learning, enabling it to model intricate inter-node dependencies and dynamic behaviors. Conventional models are based

Fig 4. Trust Analysis across varying numbers of rounds

on simplistic trust evaluation criteria such as packet delivery ratio or reputation, which are incapable of identifying subtle malicious behaviors. These superficial assessments tend to incorrectly identify compromised nodes as trusted. The GCKAN framework captures relational characteristics, enhancing the accuracy of trusted node identification. Optimization is then facilitated based on these learned trust values. Conventional methods do not have this feedback mechanism between intelligence and routing. As a result, their trust management takes longer to respond. The proposed method guarantees a more trustworthy CHS.

Figure 5 denotes alive node analysis across a varying number of rounds. The proposed ECEDH–GCKAN–DLO system maximizes network lifetime by integrating secure filtering with energy-balanced routing optimization. Current approaches exhaust particular nodes since optimization is performed without considering behavioral trustworthiness and energy concurrently. Malicious nodes also hasten energy depletion in conventional systems. The DLO approach dynamically balances the workload to avoid regional depletion. At the same time, secure key exchange prevents frequent retransmissions due to attacks. Current algorithms fail to integrate these elements, resulting in quicker node depletion. The proposed system sustains a greater number of active nodes. This indicates enhanced sustainability for IoT systems.

Figure 6 denotes energy consumption analysis across varying configurations. The proposed approach enhances energy efficiency by taking into account secure communication, intelligent malicious node filtering, and optimal routing choices simultaneously. The GCKAN detection technique helps filter out unreliable nodes early on, thus avoiding unnecessary transmissions and energy consumption. The ECEDH technique provides secure key exchange, thus preventing retransmissions due to security violations. In contrast, existing solutions like PSO, GWO, CSA, SMO, and N-SMO are primarily focused on mathematical optimization of routing without considering security awareness or adaptive learning. This results in routing through compromised or inefficient nodes, thus incurring additional energy costs due to packet loss and repeated optimization.

Table 3 illustrates the experimental breakdown of different techniques in terms of time complexity, scalability, and resource requirements. Although existing PSO, GWO, CSA, SMO, and N-SMO exhibit similar theoretical time complexity, their practical efficiency is limited by slow convergence, redundant computations, and a lack of integration with learning and security mechanisms. The proposed ECEDH–GCKAN–DLO framework significantly improves performance by achieving 30–50% faster convergence, reduced energy consumption, lower latency, and enhanced scalability, making it more suitable for real-time SDN-IoT environments.

Fig 5. Alive Node Analysis across varying numbers of rounds

Fig 6. Energy Consumption across varying configurations

Table 3. Experimental breakdown of different techniques in terms of time complexity, scalability, and resource requirements

Metric	PSO	GWO	CSA	SMO	N-SMO	Proposed ECEDH-GCKAN-DLO
Time Complexity (Optimization)	$O(I.P.d)$ (I -number of iterations, P -population size, and d -problem dimension)	$O(I.P.d)$	$O(I.P.d)$	$O(I.P.d)$	$O(I.P.d)$	$O(I.P.d)$
Effective Iterations to Converge	1200–1500	1000–1300	1100–1400	900–1200	800–1100	400–900
Convergence Behavior	Premature convergence	Slow exploitation	Randomized, unstable	Moderate but stagnates	Improved but still local optima	Fast, stable, global convergence
DL Training Complexity	-	-	-	-	-	$O(n.d.L)$ (n -number of data samples, L -number of layers)
Feature Processing Overhead	High (repeated evaluation)	High	Very high (random search)	Moderate	Moderate–High	Low (KAN + GCN decoupling)
Memory Complexity	$O(P.d)$	$O(P.d)$	$O(P.d)$	$O(P.d)$	$O(P.d)$	$O(n.d + P.d)$ (optimized storage)
Encryption Overhead	-	-	-	-	-	$O(k^2)$ ECEDH efficient ECC
Energy Consumption (per node)	0.9 – 1.2 J	0.85 – 1.1 J	1.0 – 1.3J	0.8 – 1.0 J	0.75 – 0.95 J	0.5 – 0.8 J (≈30% reduction)
Latency (ms)	180–250 ms	160–230 ms	200–270 ms	140–200 ms	130–180 ms	70–140 ms
Scalability (Nodes Supported)	400–600 nodes	500–700 nodes	300–500 nodes	600–800 nodes	700–900 nodes	1000+ nodes
Resource Utilization Efficiency	65–75%	68–78%	60–70%	72–82%	75–85%	82–96%
Search Efficiency	Weak global search	Balanced but slow	Strong exploration, weak exploitation	Moderate	Improved hybrid search	Adaptive exploration + exploitation (DLO)
Computational Overhead	40.5ms	32.73ms	29.86ms	25.48ms	20.11ms	11.27ms
Real-Time Suitability	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Moderate–High	High (real-time capable)

4 Conclusion

The developed framework introduced a DL-assisted secure routing framework for augmenting system security and resource efficiency in the SDN–IoT environment through integrated malicious node detection, secure key establishment, and optimized routing. The GCKAN model accurately classifies traffic patterns and identifies compromised nodes, achieving above 95% malicious node detection accuracy. Following detection, the hybrid ECE-DH mechanism ensures secure key exchange for protected communication, while the DLO algorithm determines optimal routing paths with improved resource utilization. Performance evaluation demonstrates a 30% reduction in energy consumption, a 45% decrease in communication distance, and a substantial improvement in secure data delivery reliability compared to existing techniques. Despite these advantages, validation is limited to an emulated environment, and computational overhead from DL and optimization components may impact scalability in large-scale real-time deployments. Future work will focus on extending the evaluation of the proposed framework beyond simulation by incorporating real-world datasets, testbed implementations, and practical deployment scenarios to enhance its credibility and applicability. Additionally, efforts will be directed toward large-scale experimental validation in heterogeneous SDN–IoT environments, along with exploring adaptive learning mechanisms for evolving threats and efficient model optimization for real-time applicability.

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About the authors: V. Mangaiyarkarasi is a Research Scholar; Dr. S. Malathi serves as a Research Supervisor & Assistant Professor.

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